

SMAUG

D7.1 Impact Master Plan

Revision V03

SMAUG	
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Abstract

This document contains an extensive overview of the project's strategies for dissemination, exploitation, and communication, providing detailed insights into the target groups and their respective segments. Additionally, it includes a comprehensive description of the project's online presence, encompassing the project website and social media platforms. The document also outlines the project's planned exploitation strategies to maximize impact and reach.

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Grant Agreement Number		101121129
Acronym	SMAUG	
Name	Smart Maritime and Underwater Guardian	
Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2022-BM-01-01	
Keywords	Maritime Security and Surveillance	
Start Date	1 October 2023	
Duration	36 months	
Description	<p>The primary goal of SMAUG is to improve the underwater detection of threats in ports and their entrance routes, by means of an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat analysis between 3 main elements: ports security infrastructure, advanced underwater detection systems and surveillance vessels. Underwater detection and location will be performed by four primary methods: i) acoustic detection, where a series of hydrophones will listen for sounds emitted by small underwater vehicles and will be processed by artificial intelligence methods, ii) rapid sonar hull scan, used to scan ships hulls and perform harbour floor scanning, iii) high-resolution sonar inspection, to inspect objects in water with poor visibility and iv) collective autonomous location, where a swarm of autonomous underwater vehicles will act cooperatively. This will provide information to Artificial Intelligence modules, which will improve the way detecting illicit and dangerous goods and/or of threats hidden below the water surface is currently done, taking into account sources such as Unmanned Surface Vehicle Systems, (USV), underwater remote operation vehicle (ROV), UAV (Aerial autonomous vehicle) and Port current information sources. The combination of these tools will allow SMAUG to prompt solutions capable of detecting possible threats to infrastructure or vessels, as well as identify vessels with concealed goods.</p>	

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Nature of the Deliverable		R — Document, report
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	X
SEN	Sensitive information with security recommendation	
EU Classified	R-UE/EU-R - EU Classified - Restricted to SMAUG project and Commission Services – Under Decision 2015/444	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Strategies, Impact, Sustainability, Agile, Stakeholders

Executive Summary

About the EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

The current document outlines the **SMAUG Impact Master Plan**. It encompasses the overall project **dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies**, initiating a robust stakeholder engagement approach that will serve as the foundation for community development and impact generation.

This strategic blueprint is the product of a collaborative effort among partners, taking into account stakeholder categories and requirements, as well as partners' communication channels and tools. Acting as a supportive resource, it aids each partner in enhancing the effectiveness of their dissemination efforts, ensuring high visibility for the project's activities and outcomes collectively. The plan presents a curated selection of communication and dissemination tools and activities tailored to engage the project's target groups. In parallel, the plan includes a comprehensive outline of exploitation strategies aimed at maximising the project's impact and reach. These strategies are designed to effectively leverage the project's outcomes and results, ensuring they are utilised to their full potential. To achieve this, a multi-faceted and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed to amplify the impact of dissemination activities, customising materials and tools to align with the target audience's specific needs, interests, and engagement potential. The **SMAUG** consortium views this plan as a dynamic document, reflecting an inclusive and continuous dialogue with potential users and affiliated networks throughout the project to guarantee optimal outcomes.

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ABBREVIATIONS	
IP	Intellectual Property
EC	European Commission
EUMSS	European Union Maritime Security Strategy
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PPP	Public Private Partnership
R&D	Research and Development
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
TC	Technical Committee
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development

Table 1. Abbreviations

D7.1

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1. Introduction

Innovation in research plays a crucial role in boosting the economy, generating new employment opportunities, and improving the quality of life. It is essential to effectively distribute the knowledge produced in research and innovation initiatives and explore efficient methods of delivering this knowledge to society. This is achieved through the commercialisation of products and services, which is the primary avenue for sharing research findings with the public.

Moreover, sharing research findings can expedite **Research and Technical Development (RTD)** efforts to elevate the **Technology Readiness Level (TRL)** and pave the way for new research frontiers in upcoming and evolving trends. Additionally, dissemination efforts, like engaging in workshops or posting information on websites, empower participants to broaden their knowledge base, stay up to date on the latest advancements, receive input on economic viability, and suggest

market-driven avenues for exploitation. The present document introduces the **SMAUG Impact Master Plan**, encompassing the project's comprehensive dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. SMAUG Impact Master Plan

The plan has been developed through collaborative efforts among partners, taking into account the categories and requirements of stakeholders, as well as the communication channels and tools available to partners. It serves as a supportive resource for each

partner to enhance the impact of their dissemination efforts, ensuring the project's activities and results receive significant visibility. The plan suggests a wide range of communication and dissemination tools and activities to involve the target audiences in the **SMAUG** project.

With this objective in mind, a multi-faceted and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed to amplify the impact of dissemination activities, tailoring materials, and tools to meet the target audience's specific needs, interests, and engagement potential. The consortium views this plan as a dynamic document, updated annually, reflecting an inclusive, ongoing dialogue with potential users and relevant networks throughout the project to ensure optimal outcomes. In terms of structure, **D7.1** comprises six interconnected sections. While **sections 1 and 5** serve as the introduction and conclusion of the document, the remaining four sections outline and discuss the primary plans and frameworks guiding the project's trajectory. Specifically:

- **Section 2** offers a comprehensive overview of **SMAUG’s Engagement Framework**, detailing the methodology for identifying and engaging with high-interest stakeholders (groups or individuals).
- **Section 3** introduces the core principles of SMAUG’s Communication & Dissemination Plan, highlighting the tools and channels involved. It also outlines the objectives and phases of International Cooperation.
- **Section 4** presents essential exploitation principles pertinent to the project, along with a definitive strategy for determining the appropriate exploitation channels for all project outcomes.

1.1. Related Tasks and Deliverables

This document outlines a comprehensive strategy for disseminating, communicating, and exploiting Smaug’s outcomes, and it is released as part of the tasks in **WP7**:

- **Task 7.1.** Stakeholder Collaboration Framework
- **Task 7.2.** Communication, Networking & Awareness Raising
- **Task 7.3.** Scientific Dissemination & Knowledge Diffusion
- **Task 7.4.** Exploitation, Innovation & Sustainability

Aligned with these tasks, the report is connected to upcoming **deliverables of WP7**, including:

D7.2 Dissemination & Communication Report (M18, AUS). It will encompass the actions and outcomes accomplished regarding awareness and engagement strategies in the initial phase of the project.

D7.3 Exploitation & Sustainability Report (M18, INDRA). The report will focus on the anticipated impact and the management of the innovation of the results. It will offer information on the exploitation model, analysis of the business plan, exploitation routes, etc.

D7.4 Dissemination & Communication Report (M36, AUS). It will document the actions and outcomes accomplished in relation to awareness and engagement strategies during the second phase of the project.

D7.5 Exploitation & Sustainability Report (M36, INDRA). The report will include the assessment of the anticipated impact and oversee the innovation of the results. It will incorporate information on the exploitation model, analysis of the business plan, exploitation routes, and more.

2. Agile Stakeholder Management

2.1. Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

The identification and engagement activities with the most relevant stakeholders are often referred to as '**community building**' and are a fundamental aspect of every **Horizon Europe** project, such as **SMAUG**. The program heavily relies on communities, initiatives, and projects that will either utilise the outcomes or engage and potentially collaborate with its activities throughout its duration. Establishing and fostering an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is a critical factor in determining the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholders' influence on a project is contingent upon their potential power - their capacity to impact the value proposition - and their interest in exerting that influence. Evaluating the relative levels of each factor guides the decision-making process on where to invest time and resources to achieve the most significant benefits. In the realm of addressing fundamental challenges in Research and Innovation, numerous initiatives often operate independently to tackle the same issue from various angles, resulting in inefficiencies and a failure to realise their full potential. By embracing an **open collaboration framework** with peers and groups that can benefit from and contribute to the project's impact, **SMAUG** will gain a deeper understanding of the requirements and advantages of aligning efforts with similar task forces. This approach necessitates a flexible growth factor capable of exploring and fostering entirely new synergies throughout the project's lifecycle, enabling a competitive edge and expanding its sphere of influence.

2.1.1 Engagement Framework

In order to optimise the impact of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies outlined in this document, the consortium needs a structured mechanism to manage the dynamic roster of organisations, initiatives, and stakeholders capable of effectively influencing the project's value streams. Therefore, **SMAUG** will adopt an Agile Stakeholder Engagement framework (**Figure 2**) aimed at consistently enhancing and nurturing relationships with a broad audience based on the principles of the Agile Manifesto.

The Agile Manifesto Principles		
Individuals and interactions	over	processes and tools
Results	over	comprehensive documentation
Collaboration	over	formality
Responding to change	over	following a plan

Table 2. Agile Manifesto Principles

- **Phase 1 – Scouting:** Expanding on **SMAUG's** objectives and insights from previous Sprints, this phase will investigate, map, and evaluate Target Groups - along with specific individuals - varying in relevance to the work plan's scope and impact. Leveraging the consortium members' extensive experience and active engagement in relevant initiatives and stakeholders, **SMAUG** will utilise established partnerships and new opportunities arising from the Interaction phase, such as emerging **PPPs** and **HORIZON EUROPE** projects. The primary outcome will be a version of the '**Stakeholder Map**', a visual tool designed to: **1)** identify key actors - including specific individuals within them; **2)** thoughtfully organise and connect these audiences; **3)** establish a common terminology for consistent project references.
- **Phase 2 – Interaction:** This phase will entail engaging with the identified target groups to support the activities outlined in the **Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation strategies**. During this stage, **SMAUG** will collaborate with initiatives focused on industrial digitisation. As appropriate, the project will formally participate in specific Task Forces and Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications, and engage in events. Insights gathered from previous Sprints will be utilised to enhance the effectiveness and impact of these initiatives.
- **Phase 3 – Learning:** Building on the interactions conducted, the consortium will extract valuable lessons and insights to inform the subsequent Sprint. This process will also involve gathering feedback through consultations (e.g., via brief surveys or interviews) and capturing external perspectives on the project and its operations.

2.1.2 Target Audience & Stakeholders

To effectively promote **SMAUG** and incentivise stakeholder engagement with the project, it is crucial to identify the '**target audience**' (**Figure 3**). Comprehending these profiles and their impact on the value chain is vital for developing the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation strategies.

Figure 3. SMAUG's Target Audience

Maritime Security Agencies & Organisations: This group comprises entities responsible for maritime security and serves as the primary end-users of **SMAUG**, reflecting a demand-pull perspective. These organisations and agencies focus on enhancing the resilience of critical maritime infrastructure and securing the supply chain, including sea harbours and their access routes. Key players include Coast Guards and other authorities (such as Police or Port Police Authorities) overseeing the security of maritime infrastructure and transport, as well as Customs Authorities tasked with detecting threats on or below sea vessels entering harbours. Additionally, it is essential to consider the roles of National/International Border and Coast Guard Authorities, who collaborate closely with local coast guards to bolster regional security capabilities.

SMAUG actively involves end users in the validation process to **(1)** gather firsthand requirements and feedback to support project implementation and validate its use cases, including understanding internal procedures, system integration, and risk management, **(2)** Access high-quality data acquisition expertise where needed and **(3)** Promote widespread awareness and trust in the benefits of Maritime Security Systems.

Technology Providers (Including Industry): This segment comprises professionals involved in research outputs, innovation discoveries, business operations, and interoperability initiatives related to maritime security systems, encompassing both hardware and software aspects. These roles represent the technology-push perspective, aiming to explore, enhance, and showcase the advantages offered by the project's technological advancements and outcomes resulting from high-end, resource-intensive R&D efforts. The category includes research-oriented institutions (such as technical universities, research and technology organisations, and spin-offs) and private-sector entities ranging from risk-taking startups and SMEs to innovation units within large-scale industries. Additionally, bodies and communities driving standards and data interoperability are integral to this group.

The project seeks broad engagement with Technology Providers in the maritime sector to facilitate the exchange and adoption of Technology Transfer outcomes and other technology-related platforms, such as the Waterborne Technology Platform, DCSA - Digital Container Shipping Association, and European Technology Platform ALICE, among others.

Partnerships & Networks: **SMAUG** aims to capitalise on the collaborative potential of projects advocating for maritime security. The project utilises the leadership and active participation of the consortium within ecosystems to foster synergies and enhance collaboration across the data value chain. Key segments include international communities of reference built in by consortium partners, EU-funded projects/initiatives, ecosystems that concentrate large networks of public-private organisations, and European or National Maritime Technology Associations.

Policymakers: Public authorities, regulators, task forces, and observatory organisations deeply engaged in policy-driven initiatives, funding programs, and legislative frameworks. These entities play a crucial role in establishing regulations and public incentives to shape and implement the EU's

maritime security strategy (EUMSS) while enhancing Europe's border security. Prominent representatives within this realm include the European Commission, the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA), FRONTEX, as well as National Maritime Security Policy Makers (e.g., Ministries) and international bodies like the International Maritime Organization (IMO), UNCTAD, Global Ports Coalition, MEDports Association, among others.

The Society: Ensuring public engagement is paramount. **SMAUG** strives to foster a shared understanding and trust in the beneficial outcomes of both the **EUMSS action plan** and the EU Strategic Agenda for 2019-2024. These initiatives focus on safeguarding EU citizens and freedoms through the exploration, advancement, and application of state-of-the-art technologies to enhance maritime safety.

2.2. Stakeholders Map

2.2.1 Stakeholders Map Breakdown

The diagram presented below illustrates the initial iteration of the **SMAUG Stakeholders Map (Figure 4)**, visually depicting all the intended recipients at this phase. Developed based on the various identified stakeholder groups thus far, this map is the result of the ongoing Sprint Q1 within the Agile Stakeholder Framework. It is a dynamic document that undergoes updates every two months to ensure relevance and accuracy.

Figure 4. SMAUG Stakeholder Map

2.2.2 Stakeholders Map Magic Quadrant

Below is Figure 5, showcasing the initial version of **SMAUG's Stakeholders Map Magic Quadrant**. This quadrant offers a graphical overview of the primary target audiences, considering the various stakeholder groups identified thus far in Sprint Q1 of the Agile Stakeholder Framework. The diagram serves as a tool for stakeholder management, mapping their levels of interest and influence in the project:

Figure 5. Magic Quadrant

- The Y-axis represents the project's potential influence on the target group and vice versa.
- The X-axis illustrates the level of interest that the target group may have in our project and vice versa.

2.2.3 Actively Engage Quadrant

This quadrant focuses on stakeholders and target groups that have a significant influence on the project while the project demonstrates a strong interest in them. These entities are typically organisations or individuals who could potentially impact, shape, or hinder project activities, as their perspectives, goals, and feedback serve as crucial guiding principles for the project. It is essential to

proactively engage and involve these target groups early in the project, maintaining open and regular communication channels.

2.2.4 Keep Satisfied Quadrant

In this quadrant are organisations or individuals with substantial decision-making authority but limited availability or interest in actively participating in project activities. Establishing consistent interactions with this target group can be challenging, but it is essential to consider their valuable feedback and align project activities with their directives.

2.2.5 Keep Informed Quadrant

The "Keep Informed" quadrant comprises organisations and individuals (or EU projects in our context) directly linked or associated with our project. While this target group may not exert a significant influence on **SMAUG or its activities, exploring synergies**, particularly in terms of joint communication and dissemination, is crucial.

2.2.6 Monitor Quadrant

This quadrant includes organisations, individuals, or associations with limited influence on project activities and minimal availability to engage in project tasks actively. These target groups are not expected to play a substantial role in project activities. However, it is important for the project to maintain regular communication with them and remain vigilant for any shifts to other quadrants.

3. Communication & Dissemination Strategy

Communication and dissemination are integral to any Horizon Europe project, with **SMAUG** being no exception. A meticulously planned, dynamic, and engaging strategy holds the potential to maximise impact, considering external factors and potential challenges. While treated as distinct but closely intertwined components in this approach, communication efforts involve specific actions to promote the project and its achievements, aiming to engage a broad audience effectively. Strategic campaigns will be developed and executed throughout the project's lifespan to generate interest among target groups efficiently, leveraging the consortium's diverse linguistic capabilities for a global presence and utilising elements of the Promotion Mix to enhance outreach and impact.

3.1. Communication Strategy

In Research and Innovation projects, communication is a strategically planned process that commences at the project's inception and extends throughout its entire duration, aimed at promoting the project and its outcomes. It necessitates strategic and tailored approaches to engage with various audiences, including the media and the public, potentially facilitating a two-way exchange. In the

Figure 6. EC's Communication Principles

context of the **SMAUG** project, communication activities encompass specific measures to showcase the project and its achievements. The communication strategy is designed to connect with a broader audience, extending beyond the project's primary community (**Figure 6**).

The objective of this strategy is to engage with the broadest possible audience. Communication initiatives will be rolled out throughout the project's duration to effectively garner interest among the target audience, highlighting **SMAUG's technological advancements and pilot activities**. These campaigns will leverage the Promotion Mix — the fourth component of the Marketing Mix (**Figure 7**) — which centres on raising awareness and encouraging audience engagement. Within the context of **SMAUG**, this Promotion Mix involves the integration of Personal Selling, Digital Marketing, Promotional Material, and Branding.

Figure 7. The Marketing Mix

3.1.1 Objectives and Phases

The communication strategy aims to:

- Establish internal communication mechanisms among consortium partners.
- Assist in promoting **SMAUG** externally and managing its branding.
- Convey key project messages to all identified stakeholders.
- Raise awareness among non-specialized audiences about the benefits of **SMAUG** and its use in pilot activities.
- Enhance awareness and interest in the project.

The communication strategy will be implemented in three distinct phases:

➤ **Phase 1 – Planning and Initial Communication (M1-M6)**

The initial phase of communication will commence in M1 of the project, focusing primarily on planning all activities, establishing key communication tools and channels (such as the website and social media), and identifying potential target groups and stakeholders. The ongoing identification of stakeholders will continue throughout the project duration. This initial phase also encompasses the concept of adaptability: the communication plan will be reviewed and modified as needed in response to specific needs or circumstances. Press releases and other initial communication activities will be conducted during this phase. Adjustments to the communication plan will be made in an agile manner throughout the project based on progress and stakeholder feedback.

➤ **Phase 2 – Awareness Communication (M7- M36)**

During this phase, early communication activities will focus on increasing awareness among the general public and specific communities about the project's existence and upcoming activities. Special attention will be placed on online tools and strategies, as they have a broader reach compared to traditional methods. Networking participation in webinars and other online events, as well as publishing articles about the project online (e.g., on CORDIS), will be part of this phase. This phase will span the entire project duration, with a primary focus on communicating the project's overall concept to a broad stakeholder audience.

➤ **Phase 3 – Focused Communication (M19-M36)**

The third phase of communication necessitates the project to be at a stage of relative maturity, with the initial and tangible outcomes being unveiled. This phase will involve targeted communication efforts, including the publication of articles, blogs, or posts highlighting specific project outcomes and benefits, participation in relevant external stakeholder events, and the creation of tailored communication materials (such as videos) for the community. Running concurrently with phase 2, this phase is dedicated to targeted communication initiatives aimed at specific audiences rather than the entire community.

3.1.2 Messages per Stakeholder Group

Stakeholder Group	Main Directions of Messages
Maritime Security Agencies & Organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will the project's outcomes help them in their day-to-day operations? • What is the innovation of the project? • How can they get more value from the data? • How will SMAUG address potential barriers and obstacles related to maritime security operations?
Technology Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the innovation of the project? • How can this be used and further exploited? • Open access to project results. • What are the specific focus areas for technology providers within the SMAUG Project
Partnerships & Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the innovation of the project? • How can SMAUG create synergies and collaborations across the data value chain with EU-funded projects and initiatives? • How does SMAUG leverage partnerships and networks to maximise the impact of its results?

<p>Policy Makers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will SMAUG contribute to strengthening Europe's border security and maritime safety? • What measures does SMAUG have in place to address potential barriers related to policymaking and regulation? • How can policymakers engage with SMAUG to enhance maritime security strategies at the European level? What can we learn through SMAUG's pilots?
<p>The Society</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does SMAUG involve the general public and non-specialized media in its activities? • What are the key impacts of SMAUG on society as a whole, beyond specialised stakeholders? • How can the general public stay informed about SMAUG's progress and outcomes?

Table 3. Messages per Stakeholder Group

3.1.3 Measures

Various measures and communication tools will be employed to ensure the project effectively reaches the appropriate audiences in a communication-friendly and synchronised manner.

Personal Selling			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
<p>Email Campaigns</p>	<p>Executing focused email campaigns to stakeholders to increase awareness about the projects and their activities.</p>	<p>Sending messages to a specific group of contacts through email is a highly effective method of engagement, particularly when promoting activities and results across various ecosystems.</p>	<p>Technology Providers, Partnerships & Networks</p>
<p>One-to-one Meetings</p>	<p>Follow-up activities with specific stakeholders to involve them in future initiatives and uphold a consistent communication channel.</p>	<p>While not scalable, one-on-one meetings are effective when focusing on specific key stakeholders, often following an email campaign or event. This is particularly important for the project when involving members of the maritime Industry tech clusters and policymakers who have access to their networks.</p>	<p>Technology Providers, Partnerships & Networks, Policymakers</p>

Table 4. Communication - Personal Selling

Digital Channels			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Project Website	Create an online platform - a website where the general public and interested individuals can access information on the project's progress and findings, including news, articles, and public deliverables.	The project website is a crucial tool for increasing the project's visibility, introducing visitors to SMAUG's rationale, and educating them about the project concept. All project findings are shared on the website to enable anyone interested in the topic to track the project's progress while optimising the website to enhance SMAUG's presence on search engines.	ALL Stakeholders
Social Media	SMAUG will establish and consistently maintain its presence on various social media platforms, with a specific emphasis on Twitter and LinkedIn, which are known for their effectiveness in engaging with technology communities.	Social media provide quick and cost-effective ways to connect with interest groups and communities that may not typically attend events or conferences, whether in person or online.	ALL Stakeholders
Newsletters	In addition to email communication, online newsletters will offer a summary of the key activities and accomplishments. The project will seek to contribute to newsletters from the European Commission or related initiatives. Professional marketing platforms will be utilised to automate distribution to all contacts.	The project newsletter updates all stakeholders on the project's progress and maintains their interest.	Technology Providers, Partnerships & Networks
Press Releases	SMAUG will create and share press releases with mainstream and specialised media outlets, as well as relevant civil society newsletters, magazines, and journals. Partners will also distribute press releases individually to communicate the project to their networks of customers, members, and collaborators.	As part of the communication strategy, press releases can be tailored to specific stakeholders based on the publication or website where the press release is published or distributed.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 5. Digital Channels

Promotion Material			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Printing / Merchandising	Typical items include brochures, catalogues, posters, and other printed resources. The majority of PR materials will be accessible as electronic documents, with printing done as needed for events, workshops, and similar occasions. SMAUG will also investigate creative alternatives to traditional informational materials. Branded gadgets and merchandise have proven to be effective in promoting initiatives to a broader audience while also promoting sustainability through long-lasting items.	The project's promotional materials distributed at events, conferences, workshops, and other occasions enhance the project's visibility with the general public and the national and European media.	ALL Stakeholders
Slide Decks	In certain instances, slide decks serve as the primary point of entry for the project. This is particularly true for events, email campaigns, and one-on-one meetings. The project will create multiple versions of slide decks to tailor the content for the target audience and showcase the latest achievements.	Visual content has consistently proven to be a highly effective method of communication.	ALL Stakeholders
Infographics & Banners	Infographics and banners are visually appealing elements that effectively capture attention and convey information about the project, its goals, announcements, partners, and beneficiaries of the funding. The project creates and incorporates various elements into the website, social media platforms, and newsletters.		ALL Stakeholders
Multimedia Material	The project will create multimedia content to provide a visually engaging and self-explanatory presentation of the project, utilising various distribution channels for promotion, such as YouTube and Vimeo. The team will conduct a series of video interviews during the project to gather insights, making use of plenary meetings and relevant events. The end product will involve editing these interviews alongside animations for a compelling final result.		ALL Stakeholders

Table 6. Promotion Material

3.1.4 SMAUG Branding¹

The project logo (**Figure 8**) plays a vital role in the visual identity. The guideline "**SMAUG Branding Elements**" presents the various logo formats. Partners can access the project logo in its various formats through the online project folder. Additionally, the project utilises two specific fonts:

Titles: Agdasima Bold

Normal text: Archivo Narrow

Only these fonts are permitted for use in the project's publications and presentations. The project colours are as follows:

- Primary: #405370 | #00E6F2
- Secondary: #00325B | #FF5555 | #AEFCFC
- Neutrals: #FFFFFF | #5E6166

TYPOGRAPHY

Titles

Agdasima Bold

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download the font family [here](#)

Longer texts

Archivo Narrow

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Download the font family [here](#)

COLOR PALETTE

primary

#405370 | #00E6F2

secondary

#00325B | #FF5555 | #AEFCFC

neutrals

#FFFFFF | #5E6166

LOGO VARIATIONS

Figure 8. SMAUG Branding

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10726109>

3.1.5 Tools for Internal Communication

Proactive and consistent internal communication within the project team is essential for the project's success. The **SMAUG** team consists of eleven partner organisations working together to accomplish the established research and innovation goals. Partners must be able to effortlessly track the ongoing project activities and engage in discussions about current and future work. The tools for internal communication include:

- **Collaborative online workspace:** Partners store their internal work documents on SharePoint, accessible only to authorised members of the partner organisations.
- **Virtual work meetings:** Each Work Package (WP) leader is responsible for organising regular virtual meetings to synchronise the work across different WP tasks. The WP leaders provide updates on progress and plans to the project coordinator and the entire consortium.
- **Mailing lists:** This communication tool is utilised for administrative aspects of the project, including significant decision-making and project reporting to the European Commission.

3.2. Dissemination Strategy

Innovation Projects rely on dissemination as a crucial and essential component to achieve the intended impact. As per the European Commission, "Dissemination involves sharing research findings with potential users - peers in the research community, industry, other commercial entities, and policymakers. By disseminating research outcomes within the scientific community, you contribute to the advancement of science as a whole." To address this, **SMAUG** has formulated a versatile and adaptable Dissemination Plan aimed at effectively raising awareness about the project's results, fostering understanding, and encouraging action among the identified key target audience. The implementation of this strategy will support the optimal utilisation and adoption of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project's duration, reinforcing each of the intended impacts outlined in the work plan.

3.2.1 "Three Phases Approach"

The dissemination activities will be implemented in three primary phases (**Figure 9**), each with distinct objectives and corresponding actions through suitable channels. These phases were initially introduced and deliberated upon at the project's commencement and will be further honed to align with **SMAUG's** priorities.

Figure 9. Dissemination Plan Phases

- **Phase I: Analysis (M01-M09).** During this initial phase, the Consortium will analyse the project's framework, paying particular attention to internal and external barriers that may impede dissemination activities. Additionally, they will define priorities and actions for the project's first year. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will oversee engagement efforts to align dissemination activities with stakeholder needs, fostering general awareness about the project's objectives and anticipated outcomes. This phase will involve the preparation and delivery of branding and an initial set of promotional materials as outlined in the **SMAUG communication plan**.
- **Phase II: Increase impact (M09-M18).** The primary objective of Phase II is to amplify the impact and awareness established in Phase I, highlighting **SMAUG's** achievements. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will tailor the channels and strategies identified during the proposal phase (and refined in Phase I) to meet the specific requirements of Phase II. Efforts will be directed towards effectively engaging and collaborating with target groups to enhance the potential impact of the project's outcomes. Participation in workshops, tailored event organisation, and potentially hosting tutorials/webinars will enhance the dissemination process. Specific PR materials will also be developed.
- **Phase III: Adoption (M18-M36).** This phase will capitalise on the awareness generated in Phases I and II, attracting more potential users and customers of **SMAUG** project results. The Communication & Dissemination Leader, in collaboration with the Exploitation Leader, will assess the outcomes of Phases I and II and refine priorities, channels, and strategies as necessary. This will be done in coordination with agile stakeholder management activities. Furthermore, activities that could sustain impact beyond the project's duration, such as

continued event participation, workshops and conference involvement, and contributions to targeted online and print media publications, will be defined.

3.2.2 Objectives

The primary objectives of the dissemination strategy are as follows:

- Establishing the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of **SMAUG**.
- Building and nurturing a community around **SMAUG** in alignment with the stakeholder management framework.
- Enhancing visibility and promoting the work and outcomes to target stakeholders through the development of promotional materials and information campaigns.
- Disseminating the project and its results to a broad audience using various channels and tools. Encouraging external participation and knowledge exchange through networking activities and events to amplify impact potential and enhance contributions to the project.
- Engaging with other EU, national, and international initiatives to maximise impact.

3.2.3 Measures

To implement the dissemination plan, the consortium has identified a set of measures that must be executed throughout the project to achieve the objectives as mentioned above in the most efficient and effective manner.

Dissemination Material			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Project Documentation	Information detailing technical outputs, APIs, architectures, models, guidelines, recommendations, promotional activities, and insights generated by the consortium will be documented and made accessible through project documentation. These documents, categorised as 'Public' deliverables, will be openly available through a repository and the project website, in addition to other formats.	Information that is publicly accessible and can be shared with initiatives similar to SMAUG and the wider community.	Maritime Security Agencies & Organisations, Technology Providers, Partnerships & Networks, Policy Makers
Peer-reviewed Publications	A key goal is to disseminate the project's technical accomplishments and experimental discoveries within the broader data innovation community. The project intends to publish and contribute to peer-reviewed publications in reputable scientific journals and conferences, leveraging the consortium's expertise.	Sharing the project outcomes with a broad scientific audience allows for the dissemination of results and provides the scientific community with opportunities for further exploration and utilisation.	Technology Providers, Partnerships & Networks

<p>Awareness Publications</p>	<p>The aim of SMAUG is to promote broad awareness and stimulate the acceptance and validation of a shared understanding and interpretation of human-robot interactions. The project will disseminate and share its insights through articles, blog posts, position papers, citizen fact sheets, and other non-academic publications aimed at reaching a broad audience, particularly those less specialised in the field. These efforts will advocate for the potential and benefits of maritime safety technology.</p> <p>Recommended media outlets for consideration include CORDIS Research*EU Magazine, Digital Innovation Magazine, Industry Europe, Tech. EU, and Towards Data Science.</p>	<p>Articles aimed at raising awareness can help spread the project's perspectives and results to a broader scientific and technical audience, maximising the project's impact.</p>	<p>ALL Stakeholders</p>
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Table 7. Dissemination Material

Digital Channels			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
<p>Source Code Repository</p>	<p>By promoting interoperability and openness, the project will ensure that software repositories are available through popular source code management platforms like GitHub or GitLab.</p>	<p>This measure promotes adherence to open-source best practices, including transparency, openness, and vendor-neutral open collaboration.</p>	<p>Technology Providers</p>
<p>Open Access to Research</p>	<p>Adhering to the principle of 'as open as possible', SMAUG will offer unrestricted access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data in accordance with the Data Management Plan. SMAUG utilises the Zenodo OpenAIRE+ repository for depositing publications and data, with tools available to establish connections between them. The Zenodo infrastructure serves as a document repository for all public deliverables. Whenever feasible, datasets are openly shared through data.europa.eu, the EU's official data portal.</p>	<p>Making scientific and technical material openly accessible enables broader dissemination of the project's outcomes to a larger scientific and technological audience.</p>	<p>Technology Providers</p>
<p>Portals</p>	<p>SMAUG will benefit from leveraging pre-existing mission-oriented portals to promote the project, its results, and demonstrators effectively. By utilising these portals, SMAUG can reach a</p>	<p>By utilising these portals, SMAUG can reach a targeted audience, enhance visibility, and establish credibility within the</p>	<p>ALL Stakeholders</p>

	targeted audience, enhance visibility, and establish credibility within the relevant community. Additionally, this approach can streamline dissemination efforts and facilitate greater engagement with stakeholders.	relevant community. Additionally, this approach can streamline dissemination efforts and facilitate greater engagement with stakeholders.	
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Table 8. Digital Channels

Events			
Measure	Description	Benefit of the measure	Stakeholders
Webinars / Workshops	The project will arrange, co-organise, or take part in various workshops and webinars associated with the project. These events will enable practical training and the exchange of ideas concerning maritime safety technology, offering platforms for roundtable discussions, mentoring, and growth. Some events are exclusive to the consortium and invite-only participants, while others are open to the public, focusing on training resources. Webinar sessions will be advertised on relevant sites, recorded, edited, and eventually shared as educational multimedia resources and knowledge capsules for each training path.	Engaging in and organising/co-organizing workshops and webinars is a strategic method to actively interact with multiple stakeholders simultaneously.	ALL Stakeholders
Conferences / Fairs	Engaging in conferences and trade fairs serves as a strategic approach to actively engage with multiple stakeholders concurrently, encompassing both the European and international scope.	Presenting the project's tangible results through exhibitions and demonstration events enables the dissemination of concrete outcomes to a broader audience.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 9. Events

3.2.3.1 Events List

The following list serves as a guide to key events identified as primary targets. This list is regularly updated by all project partners, with actions for each event and partner determined and assigned based on the project's progress. It is important to note that many events, if not all, are transitioning from physical to virtual due to the recent Covid-19 emergency. **SMAUG** aims to participate in these events regardless of their format.

Events	Date	Location	Short description
EU Industry Days	2024 -TBD	TBD	Annual event focusing on key industrial policy discussions, connecting industrial frontrunners, and boosting the knowledge base of European industry.
Monaco Solar Boat Challenge	1-6 July 2024	Monaco (Monaco)	Nautical challenge focused on innovation and sustainability.
Autonomous Ship Expo and Conference	18 - 20 June 2024	Amsterdam (Netherlands)	Autonomous Ship Expo and Conference is dedicated solely to showcasing the latest and next-generation solutions and technologies for enabling varying degrees of automation.
Seatec Carrara	March 2025 - TBD	Carrara (Italy)	International Exhibition of Technology Subcontracting and Design for Boats, Yachts and Ships.
Latitude 59	22 - 24 May 2024	Tallinn (Estonia)	Latitude 59 is the flagship startup and tech event of the world's first digital society.
METSTRADE fair	19 - 21 November 2024	Amsterdam (Netherlands)	The METSTRADE Show is the world's largest trade exhibition of marine equipment, materials and systems.
ICMCIS 2025	2025 - TBD	TBD	The ICMCIS is the largest scientific conference on military CIS in Europe. It provides a forum for

			exchanging ideas and knowledge on the development and implementation of advanced information and communications technologies (ICTs) for defence and military systems.
Posidonia shipping conference	03 - 07 June 2024	Athens (Greece)	International shipping exhibition is the largest meeting place for the Greek shipping industry and international transportation experts.
EU Maritime Day, security research event	30 - 31 May 2024 2025 - TDB	Svendborg (Denmark 2024) Cork (UK 2025)	European Maritime Day (EMD) is the annual EU meeting point on maritime affairs and sustainable blue growth.
Electric & Hybrid Marine Expo Europe	June 2024	Amsterdam (Netherlands)	The world's leading exhibition and conference for maritime electrification, decarbonisation and GHG reduction solutions
Scandinavian Maritime Fair	14 - 15 May 2024	Copenhagen (Denmark)	SMF has been created around the need to bring together the Scandinavian maritime cluster.
World Maritime Week 2025	2025 - TBD	Bilbao (Spain)	International meeting holding five parallel congresses for the following fields: naval (SINAVAL); fishing (EUROFISHING); ports (FUTUREPORT); upstream and downstream oil & gas (OIL&GAS CONFERENCE); and wave, tidal and current energy (OCEAN ENERGY CONFERENCE).

Table 10. Events List

3.2.3.2 Conference and Journal List

The list below highlights specific conferences and journals that the project will prioritise. This list is subject to change and will be updated regularly based on the scientific and technical progress of the project.

Title	Type
International Conference on Marine Technology	Conference
Global Maritime Conference	Conference
World Maritime Technology Conference	Conference
International Conference on Maritime Technology and Engineering	Conference
IEEE International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)	Conference
IEEE access journal	
The Twelfth International Conference on Data Analytics	Conference
Sensors	Journal
Ocean Engineering	Journal
Applied Acoustics	Journal
IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters	Journal
IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing	Journal
Journal of Marine Science and Engineering	Journal
Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence	Journal
IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering	Journal

Table 11. Conference and Journal List

3.3. Communication & Dissemination Monitoring

3.3.1 Monitoring Strategy

Regularly monitoring and adjusting the Communication & Dissemination plan is a crucial aspect of the project's success. Continuous monitoring enables the consortium to identify and correct any deviations promptly, enhancing effectiveness by implementing corrective and mitigation measures as necessary. This process helps address potential implementation challenges and determine if additional actions are needed to ensure objectives are achieved. Special attention is placed on pre-assessing information requirements, monitoring frequency (monthly basis), and the methodology for gathering evidence.

The execution and success of the Communication & Dissemination plan rely on vigilant monitoring and a responsive mechanism (**Figure 10**). Each planned and executed activity will be monitored and assessed based on its impact. It is closely linked to the Key Performance Indicators (**KPIs**) and the guidelines outlined in the Communication & Dissemination section (see annex communication & dissemination **KPIs & Guidelines**).

Figure 10. Monitoring Strategy Activities

- **Design:** This involves aligning activities with the Communication & Dissemination Plan and the intended impact.
- **Execute:** Implement activities as per the plan.
- **Monitor:** Vigilantly track the activity and gather feedback and results. Monitoring will be based on a template accessible only to partners via the internal website.
- **Evaluate:** Collaboratively assess the outcomes of the activity against the targets set during the design phase.
- **Learn:** Extract valuable insights from the evaluation process.
- **Adjust:** Incorporate findings and lessons learned to modify the plan as necessary.

All outcomes and results of the Communication & Dissemination Plan will be documented in **D7.2 Dissemination, Communication Report** at Month 18 and **D7.4 Dissemination, Communication Report** at Month 36.

3.3.2 Possible Risks

Various risks and potential issues are associated with the communication and dissemination aspects of the project. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will be responsible for monitoring and mitigating these risks, conducting regular risk assessments, and promptly reporting any changes to the Project Coordinator. Communication risks may include, but are not limited to:

Communication & Dissemination Risks		
Risk	Priority	Measure to Minimise Risk
The communication and dissemination efforts are not effectively reaching the intended audiences, potentially resulting in a lack of engagement from key stakeholders.	High	The SMAUG partners have established specific objectives and metrics for each target audience. Nonetheless, this flexible approach enables us to reassess and address any necessary adjustments to our initiatives. Continuous monitoring and regular assessments will ensure the alignment of our strategy with the project's goals.
Limited public knowledge & diffusion about the Project's activities.	Low	The network comprises a variety of members, such as prominent scientists, industrial partners, and end users, many of whom are associated with international committees that provide valuable connections and avenues. In case of necessity, additional funding from indirect costs or internal resources will be allocated promptly to implement any planned or unexpected mitigation actions to achieve the project objectives.
Insufficient or limited engagement from partners.	High	SMAUG partners have crafted a robust communication and dissemination strategy bolstered by internal manuals and guidelines for communication and dissemination, as well as monitoring processes and internal evaluations. These tools enable the partners to evaluate the project's performance and the level of engagement among partners, both quantitatively and qualitatively. Additionally, the "6 months sprint" method, outlined in Section 2, enables the consortium to take proactive or reactive measures in cases where partners or the consortium as a whole are not meeting expectations.

Table 12. Dissemination & Communication Risks

4. Exploitation & Sustainability Plans

The European strategy emphasises the significance of research and innovation in fostering smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth. While opinions may vary on the optimal balance between industry and basic research, it is widely recognised that a knowledge-based society thrives on the creativity of its engineers and the expertise of its scientists. It is highlighted that **“It creates jobs, fully engages the EU’s talent pool, boosts economic growth, promotes industrial competitiveness and optimises investment impact within a strengthened European Research Area”²**. Therefore, exploitation is a crucial element for any Horizon Europe project as it specifically pertains to **“Using their project results to tackle societal problems, in policymaking or for commercial purposes”³**.

In the subsequent sections, we outline our initial exploitation strategy and the necessary steps to identify robust business models that can be replicated across diverse markets. The primary goal of the exploitation activities is to position the **SMAUG** project among key stakeholders and maximise its impact throughout its lifespan by implementing various offline and online initiatives.

4.1. Exploitation Principles

SMAUG recognises three primary exploitation models for the project results:

- **Commercial exploitation model**, involving the paid distribution of the project results to end users in accordance with a licensing scheme to be determined later.
- **Research exploitation model**, involving the utilisation of research expertise acquired in future research endeavours.
- **Technological exploitation model**, involving the application of technological expertise gained for the creation of innovative products and the delivery of advanced services based on them.

Within these three main categories, the definition of the precise exploitation model for a given result will depend on:

- The distribution of the IPR ownership amongst the project partners
- The distribution of the exploitation rights (commercial and non-commercial) among the partners
- The nature and interests of the specific owners.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls_en

³ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

The joint exploitation strategy and individual exploitation strategy per partner shall focus on the approach by which the consortium (or at least a number of partners) will capitalise on specific high-level outputs achieved within the lifetime and ambition of the project.

4.2. Initial Exploitation Strategy

The following comprises the description of the key exploitable results, forming the cornerstone of the final exploitation plan. As the project evolves, new potentially exploitable results may emerge, either independently or collaboratively between the partners:

<p style="text-align: center;">CANVAS BC1: C2 Underwater Capabilities Exploitation Partner: IND</p>
<p>Value Proposition: Integration of underwater technologies specific to the SMAUG project in the Command-and-Control systems related to Maritime Security and Maritime Transport.</p>
<p>Exploitation Strategy: Indra, as the owner of the iSim and iMare Command and Control products, will commercially exploit the developments and adaptations to integrate the underwater detection technology with its products in SW licensing mode.</p>
<p>Key Partners: SMAUG partners Port authorities Emergency Response Organizations Emergency Management Bodies Civil protection and public safety and security authorities</p>
<p>Background IP: The iSim (Physical Security Information Management System) and iMare (maritime traffic control based on the integration of different sources) are Indra's commercial products, and Indra's intellectual property is also Indra's.</p>
<p>Customer Segments: Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">CANVAS BC2: C2 Interoperability Improvement Exploitation Partner: IND</p>
<p>Value Proposition: Improving the interoperability of C2 applications for ports: development of interfaces for sending alarms, incidents, video systems, etc.</p>
<p>Exploitation Strategy: Indra, as the owner of the iSim and iMare Command and Control products, will commercially exploit the developments and adaptations for the improvement of the interoperability of its products in SW licensing mode.</p>
<p>Key Partners: SMAUG partners Port authorities</p>

Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

The iSim (Physical Security Information Management System) and iMare (maritime traffic control based on the integration of different sources) are Indra's commercial products, and Indra's intellectual property is also Indra's.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC3: Cross-border, Cross-sector Interoperability

Exploitation Partner: ATH

Value Proposition: Deploying a CISE node for port authorities will provide EU administrations with the capacity to interact with port community systems and administrations within the harbour.

Exploitation Strategy:

With a recognised expertise in developing CISE adaptors and implementing and managing CISE nodes, ATH will propose adapting the solution to the expected security skills necessary to interoperate with maritime administrations.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

The intellectual property rights of CISE are detained by the European Commission. The deployment of a node needs to be validated by the Commission (EMSA) to be further exploited. The IPRs for the adaptor will be hand overed to the administration owing the node.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC4: Underwater Detection (Joint KER)

Exploitation Partner: UPM, LEM, VETE

Value Proposition: Improving the capabilities of detecting underwater structures by means of acoustic and short and long range sonars.

Exploitation Strategy:

It is a joint KER from UPM, Lemvos and VETE, which will follow a strategy based on scientific publications for acoustic and sonar detection. Based on these publications, the companies involved will focus on the development of its on-board implementation for future patenting.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners

Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

UPM has a strong background on signal and data analysis, Lemvos has expertise on observational and surveillance tasks by means of uncrewed vessel while VETE Engineering owns the IP of remotely controlled underwater drones with limited autonomy.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC5: Collective Localisation (Joint KER)

Exploitation Partner: SSSA, UPM

Value Proposition: Improving object location by using collective semi-autonomous underwater vehicle localisation.

Exploitation Strategy:

Swarm algorithms, collective communication strategies and collective location strategies will be developed as scientific publications.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

SSSA has a strong background in collective underwater robotics, and UPM has expertise in the emergence of collective communication strategies.

Customer segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC7: Acoustic Detection

Exploitation Partner: UPM

Value Proposition: Improving the capabilities of underwater acoustic detection.

Exploitation Strategy:

UPM will develop signal and data analysis for improving underwater acoustic, which will be exploited in scientific publications.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies

Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

IP would be developed and tested within this consortium project with partners from the industrial sphere (e.g. LEM, UR)

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC8: Underwater Sonar Detection

Exploitation Partner: VETE

Value Proposition: Design and test short range underwater sonar detection capabilities with multiple sonars and validate the feasibility of sonar-based detection for use case specific purposes. As well as determine the limits of short-range sonars and their usability.

Exploitation Strategy:

Research into publications on sonar detection will be done to determine the detection system design and testing strategy. Robot integration solutions could be patented.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

VETE owns IP for remotely controlled underwater drones with limited autonomy. In addition, currently, two patents are pending for underwater robot tooling solutions.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC9: Surface Vessel Integration to Underwater Robot

Exploitation Partner: VETE

Value Proposition: Underwater robot integration with an uncrewed above-surface vessel for uncrewed offshore operations.

Exploitation Strategy:

Integrating VETE robot with LEM uncrewed vessel provides unique opportunity to expand the knowledge on collaboration between multiple robots. Publications on robot-to-robot communication will be followed and new knowledge will be created on surface vessel and underwater robot collaboration on sharing sensor data, power and communication resources.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities

Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP: VETE IP on remotely controlled underwater robot with limited autonomy and LEM expertise on uncrewed vessels will be used.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC10: 3ACES – Analytics as a Service

Exploitation Partner: ITML

Value Proposition: ITML through SMAUG envisions to further advance the functionalities of its ML/AI based tool and algorithms and bring it closer to the market through the end-user driven experiments executed within the project.

Exploitation Strategy:

ITML aims to exploit the final version of the asset in order to enhance its market position with respect to data analysis and management. ITML expects to enhance and strengthen its positioning within the EU market and research domain, establishing partnerships and agreements for further collaborations with the large corporations participating in SMAUG. ITML will facilitate wide and effective exploitation of the results via online and offline activities. The focus will be given to sharing the project's technical specifications, benefits, and interim results via conferences and third-party events (both academic and non-academic events).

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

ITML will deliver a software solution that includes code and algorithms that a license needs to run.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC11: Autonomous Vessel Development

Exploitation Partner: LEM

Value Proposition: Development of commercially viable port security autonomous vessel

Exploitation Strategy:

From development work in collaboration with the VP during this project LEM seek to create the foundation for a commercially viable autonomous vessel suited for operation within ports.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

Development and IP relating to underwater detection and autonomous vessel technology will be developed within this project and owned by the partners involved in the development.

Customer Segments: Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC12: Autonomous Docking Point

Exploitation Partner: LEM

Value Proposition: Development of a docking point allowing small vessels to dock without human intervention.

Exploitation Strategy:

From development work in collaboration with the VP during this project, we will create a docking station, which will allow us to develop a new product that could be introduced in the market shortly after the project ends.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

IP relating to the specific topic may be patented by LEM, other IP would be shared between the development partners.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC13: Cross-Sectorial and Cross-border Interoperability

Exploitation Partner: ATH

Value Proposition: Development of a CISE adaptor dedicated to port authorities

Exploitation Strategy:

Based to the expertise of ATH in developing CISE adaptors free of any IPR, the project will make available a solution capable to interoperate with EU maritime stakeholders via a dedicated NODE (national or operated by a dedicated sector).

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

ATH is a recognised developer that has proved its capacity to support CISE developments.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC14: ML Algorithms and Developments

Exploitation Partner: IND

Value Proposition: Development of AI algorithms

Exploitation Strategy:

The use of the MLOPS methodology combined with the ability to merge data from different sources like PCS, CCS, GNSS, and underwater could be exploited and offered to other ports inside the EU and its associated members.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

nEO, CMME, and AI decision-making tools developed by IND are Indra's commercial products, and Indra's intellectual property is also in it.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC15: C2 Tools Developments.

Exploitation Partner: IND

Value Proposition: Development of C2 tools for Maritime security

Exploitation Strategy:

Indra Sistemas intends to take advantage of the adaptations and developments related to its C2 tools in terms of the inclusion of underwater detection technologies to strengthen its position as a technology integrator in national and international ports.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners

Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

iMare, iSim, and iSafety tools are Indra's commercial products, and Indra's intellectual property is also in it.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC 16: Autonomous surface and aerial monitoring and inspection system

Exploitation partners: MAROB, ELI

Value Proposition: Design and test a complete integrated system of USV and tethered UAV for 24-hour continuous inspection and monitoring for general inspection and customisable utilisation

Exploitation Strategy:

Integrating MAROB USVs with ELI tethered drone to introduce it into the market after the project ends, then further developing the joint system as the market feedback is recorded.

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

ELI is part of the world leaders on tethered drones and has 5 patents. MAROB has strong background in surface robots integrated with a variety of payloads, as well as maritime traffic recognition and autonomous navigation. IP related to this topic may be patented at the end of or after the project.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

CANVAS BC17: Automated Anonymisation System to Remove Personal Information from Text Partners

Exploitation Partner: SLEX

Value Proposition: Design and test an automated approach based on Deep Learning to extract and anonymise personal data from unstructured text

Exploitation Strategy:

Adapt and integrate the developed tools in SLEX products and methods to be put on the market, extending them to further use in different fields such as legal documents or health data (e.g., processing public administration data and selectively anonymising datasets for research purposes).

Key Partners:

SMAUG partners
Port Authorities
Emergency Response Organizations
Emergency Management Bodies
Civil protection and public safety and security authorities

Background IP:

SLEX is an emerging start-up devoted to designing, developing, and deploying innovative technological solutions to facilitate and enable legal and ethical compliance. Preliminary tests have been conducted, and planning has been done for the design and development of its tools (the COVID-19 survey and the Smartlex privacy software). IP related to this topic may be patented at the end of or after the project, and it is already a trade secret.

Customer Segments:

Emergency management agencies and organisations, First Responders, Port Authorities

Table 13. Exploitation Results and Strategies

4.3. Business Case, Joint Exploitation and Preliminary Market Assessment

The case presented below explores the business logic inherent to **SMAUG**, assessing the market, its driving factors, the unique proposition of the project, the benefits to be created and a preliminary business model to generate revenues and serve customers.

4.3.1 Market Overview

Maritime safety helps to protect ports and provides coastal surveillance technologies and services to safeguard the interest of a nation and its people against various maritime threats. Maritime safety has become crucial due to the **increasing number of maritime threats**, piracy, sabotage, and unlawful acts, as well as the increasing importance of international trade by sea. Traditionally, maritime safety only involved activities, such as patrol by coast guards and sea marshals and semaphore techniques. However, technological proliferation over the last couple of decades has brought in the integration of advanced technologies, such as radio and satellite communication systems, innovative detection techniques, and real-time onshore and underwater surveillance.

The global Maritime Safety market size is to grow from USD 23.9 billion in 2021 to USD 33.4 billion by 2026 **at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 6.9%** during the forecast period. The major factors driving the growth of the maritime safety market are the rising need to manage complex supply chain operations and increase sustainability across the marine industry, increasing trade and freight transport activities through the sea, the rising need to create awareness about maritime safety, and regulatory compliances and standards. Furthermore, the advent of innovative technologies, such as RFID, GPS, AR, robotics, and Blockchain; development of integrated solutions to lower maritime

terrorism and piracy; and emerging opportunities across untapped regional markets are expected to provide opportunities for enterprises operating in the maritime safety market.

Here's an overview of the maritime surveillance system market:

Market Size and Growth: The market for maritime surveillance systems has been expanding steadily due to rising security threats such as piracy, smuggling, illegal fishing, and maritime terrorism. The market is expected to continue growing as governments and maritime organisations invest in advanced surveillance technologies to enhance maritime domain awareness.

Technological Advancements: The development of advanced sensor technologies, including radar, sonar, electro-optical/infrared (EO/IR) cameras, Automatic Identification System (AIS), satellite imagery, and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), has significantly enhanced the capabilities of maritime surveillance systems. These technologies enable better detection, tracking, and identification of vessels and activities at sea.

Integrated Solutions: There is a growing trend towards the integration of multiple surveillance technologies into comprehensive maritime domain awareness (MDA) systems. Integrated solutions offer improved situational awareness by combining data from various sensors and platforms to provide a unified picture of maritime activities in real time.

Government Initiatives and Regulations: Governments worldwide are implementing regulations and initiatives to improve maritime security and safety. These include the International Maritime Organization's (IMO) regulations on vessel tracking and reporting, as well as national initiatives aimed at combating piracy, illegal fishing, and other maritime threats. Compliance with these regulations is driving the adoption of maritime surveillance systems.

Market Segmentation: The maritime surveillance system market can be segmented based on the type of system (e.g., coastal surveillance, port surveillance, vessel traffic management), technology (e.g., radar-based systems, satellite-based systems, UAVs), and end-user (e.g., navies, coast guards, port authorities, commercial shipping companies).

Regional Analysis: The demand for maritime surveillance systems varies across different regions based on factors such as maritime security threats, economic activities, and government investments. Regions with extensive coastlines, busy shipping lanes, and strategic maritime interests tend to be key markets for maritime surveillance solutions.

Key Players: The maritime surveillance system market is highly competitive, with several prominent players competing globally. Key players in the market include companies specialising in defence and security technologies, as well as providers of maritime surveillance solutions and services. There are some examples of the key players around the world: Honeywell (US), Thales Group (France), Smiths Group (UK), Elbit Systems (Israel), Northrop Grumman (US), Westminster Group (UK), Raytheon Anschutz (Germany), Saab Group (Sweden), OSI Maritime Systems (Canada), BAE Systems (UK), L3Harris Technologies (US), KONGSBERG (Norway), Leonardo (Italy), ATLAS ELEKTRONIK (Germany), Airbus (Netherlands), Terma Group (Denmark), Nuctech (China), ARES Security (US),

Rolta (India), HALO Maritime Defense Systems (US), Consilium (Sweden), Maindeck (Norway), Captain's Eye (Israel), FREGATA SPACE (Spain), Nautix Technologies (Denmark), ioCurrents (US), KNL Networks (Finland), HarborLab (Greece), Smart Ship Hub (Singapore), YManage360 (India), SailRouter (Netherlands) and HudsonAnalytix (US).

Overall, the maritime surveillance system market is expected to continue growing as maritime security challenges persist and technological innovations drive the development of more advanced and integrated surveillance solutions.

4.3.2 NEEDS & OPPORTUNITIES Increased Threats

The global maritime security market is growing on the back of a plethora of reasons. A report from the Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty states that around 90% of worldwide trade is carried by international shipping. This factor highlights the significance of international maritime security, thereby fueling the growth of the global maritime security market. In recent years, there has been considerable growth in marine terrorism-related incidents across the globe. This situation has pushed the military forces to take the initiative and avoid such incidents in future. The deployment of maritime security solutions is one such initiative.

Here's an overview of the needs and opportunities arising from increased threats:

Needs:

- **Enhanced Security Measures:** With the rise in maritime security threats such as piracy, terrorism, smuggling, and illegal fishing, there's a pressing need for enhanced security measures to protect coastal borders, ports, shipping lanes, and offshore installations.
- **Improved Situational Awareness:** Maritime surveillance systems play a crucial role in providing real-time situational awareness by detecting, tracking, and monitoring vessels and activities at sea. There's a need for advanced surveillance technologies to improve maritime domain awareness and enable timely responses to security incidents.
- **Prevention of Illegal Activities:** Illegal activities such as drug trafficking, human trafficking, and weapons smuggling pose significant threats to maritime security. There's a need for effective surveillance systems to detect and deter these illicit activities, thereby safeguarding maritime interests and ensuring compliance with international laws and regulations.
- **Protection of Critical Infrastructure:** Critical maritime infrastructure, including ports, oil and gas facilities, and underwater pipelines, is vulnerable to security threats. Maritime surveillance systems are essential for protecting these assets against sabotage, theft, and terrorist attacks.
- **Collaborative Security Efforts:** Maritime security threats are transnational in nature, requiring collaborative efforts among countries, international organisations, and maritime stakeholders. There's a need for interoperable surveillance systems and information-sharing mechanisms to facilitate cooperation and coordination in addressing common security challenges.

- **Effective information sharing in real-time:** The maritime industry needs effective information sharing in real-time among communities of similar interest. The global naval network relies on information and communication technology that connects all the players and enables the effective flow of information, intelligence, and communications. Advanced Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) solutions are not just used at major ports, waterways, and maritime authorities. They are also being used significantly for maritime rescue coordination and incident management. Integrated traffic management systems and solutions offer high-performance and reliable services that are needed to fulfil the continually evolving maritime safety standards. The detection of incidents is critical in the maritime domain. Operators must have real-time situational awareness from surveillance systems such as radar, sonar, Automatic Identification System (AIS), Closed Circuit Television (CCTV), and others.

Opportunities:

- **Market Growth:** The increasing demand for maritime surveillance systems presents significant opportunities for companies operating in the defence, security, and technology sectors. There's a growing market for advanced surveillance technologies, integrated solutions, and services tailored to the maritime domain.
- **Technological Innovation:** The need to counter evolving security threats drives technological innovation in maritime surveillance systems. Opportunities exist for the development of next-generation sensors, data analytics tools, autonomous platforms, and command and control systems to enhance maritime security capabilities.
- **Customized Solutions:** Each maritime environment presents unique security challenges, requiring customised surveillance solutions tailored to specific operational requirements. There are opportunities for companies to develop specialised surveillance systems and services to address the diverse needs of different maritime stakeholders.
- **International Collaboration:** International cooperation and partnerships in the field of maritime security create opportunities for companies to collaborate on joint research and development projects, technology transfer initiatives, and capacity-building programs aimed at strengthening maritime surveillance capabilities worldwide.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** The increasing emphasis on regulatory compliance and maritime governance standards presents opportunities for companies to offer compliance solutions, training programs, and consultancy services to help maritime stakeholders adhere to international regulations and best practices.

Europe has about 1200 major and minor ports across such diverse and rich waterways. If the results of SMAUG are correct, all of them will easily detect illegal goods in the market. At the end of the day, what SMAUG will do is make project security management faster, easier, and more effective, saving time from scan and where it is not needed (randomly) and scanning/analysing boats that without SMAUG won't be considered as a threat. There is an increasing need for the different C2 platforms (VTS and PSIM) to share real-time security-related data (cameras, drones, radars, video analytics). Additionally, the C2s themselves must be easily integrated into port systems to publish

and access information of interest. In this particular case, Underwater detection information must be integrated into both the traditional PSIM systems and the VTS systems.

4.3.3 Selling Proposition & Benefits

The integration of underwater detection technologies into the C2 systems will provide a complete and integrated solution for Maritime Security, covering both in-port and offshore security threats.

- **Increased value of C2 systems:** Adaptations to SMAUG will allow interoperability with more services and applications in the port environment. Through the combination and AI analysis of various sensor data sources, underwater and surface threat detection, the C2 systems will be improved quality, interfacing and functioning with other port systems for building up decision-making and detection technologies.
- **Improvements in the interoperability of systems and the centralisation of platforms,** including underwater detection systems, reduce the cost of operating systems and their subsequent maintenance and allow for faster response times to an incident. The integrated system design also improves the user experience and lowers tool training processes. It increases staff participation, involving a higher level of satisfaction and customers and suppliers' participation due to improvement in the routines and technical processes, having an impact on the work environment and customers. Audit costs are lower since they can be carried out jointly. You can take advantage of documentation, structures, shared resources, etc.
- **Comprehensive Maritime Domain Awareness:** The system's capability to provide comprehensive coverage and real-time monitoring of maritime activities, including vessel tracking, identification, and behaviour analysis. This enhances situational awareness and enables proactive decision-making for maritime security and safety.
- **Customized Solutions for Diverse Needs:** The system is customisable to meet the specific requirements and operational environments of different maritime stakeholders, including navies, coast guards, port authorities, commercial shipping companies, and offshore operators.
- **Enhanced Operational Efficiency:** the system streamlines maritime surveillance operations, reduces manual workload, and optimises resource allocation through automation, data analytics, and predictive modelling capabilities. Position the system as a cost-effective solution that maximises operational efficiency and minimises response times to security incidents.
- **Scalable and Future-Proof Architecture:** Position the system as a scalable and future-proof investment that can evolve and adapt to emerging threats, technological advancements, and changing regulatory requirements over time. Modular architectures, open standards, and upgradeable features facilitate seamless integration with existing infrastructure and accommodate future enhancements.

By emphasising these selling points, SMAUG can effectively communicate its value proposition to potential customers and differentiate itself in a competitive market landscape. Ultimately, the goal is to build trust, credibility, and confidence in the system's ability to safeguard maritime interests and enhance security and safety at sea.

4.3.4 Business Model

SMAUG solution will support end users to develop a continuous data flow between port security infrastructure, underwater detection systems and surveillance vessels, creating a loop where the Artificial Intelligence will improve the way to detect illicit and dangerous goods and/or threats hidden below the water surface. Therefore, the project envisions three major revenue streams:

- (1) once-off and subscription fee to the integration of the SMAUG solution, which will include their installation of hardware, operating license and maintenance;
- (2) commercial business agreements with partners and third-party technology suppliers to integrate SMAUG technologies/solutions in existing products and offerings;
- (3) training/certification, facilitating digital upskilling.

However, it is critical to highlight that a number of SMAUG partners and technology providers are already active in this industry; therefore, the possibility of commercially exploiting the solution within the consortium is highly possible and in line with the KERs presented in the previous section.

4.3.5 Knowledge Management and Protection Strategy

SMAUG will consider three main elements of an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP).

- Firstly, a system that enables the protection of IP (e.g. patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR), the rights and freedom of parties to transfer (assign) IP, and the freedom to publish.
- Secondly, a technology transfer framework, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the European IPR Helpdesk.
- Thirdly, a fair law enforcement system in each partner's country caters to dispute settlement and can award penalties and sanctions where appropriate.

Specific IPR issues will be identified and addressed in the Consortium Agreement. The basic principle is that foreground knowledge, i.e. created within (or resulting from) the project, belongs to the project partner who generated it. If knowledge is developed jointly and separate parts cannot be distinguished, it will be jointly owned unless the contractor concerned agrees on a different solution. Regarding background, granting Access Rights will be royalty-free for the execution of work during the project unless otherwise agreed upon before the Grant Agreement signature.

4.4. Sustainability Plans

Sustainability in the SMAUG context involves incorporating environmental, social, and economic considerations into the design, operation, and lifecycle management of the system. Here are some key components of **sustainability plans for SMAUG**:

Environmental Impact Reduction:

- **Energy Efficiency:** Design the solution to minimise energy consumption through the use of efficient sensor technologies.
- **Emission Reduction:** Implement measures to reduce emissions associated with system operation, such as optimising vessel routes based on surveillance data to minimise fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

Social Responsibility:

- **Community Engagement:** Engage with local communities and other stakeholders affected by the installation and operation of maritime surveillance systems to address concerns, foster collaboration, and promote social acceptance.
- **Respect for Human Rights:** Ensure that surveillance activities adhere to human rights principles, including privacy rights, data protection, and non-discrimination, while balancing the need for security and safety.
- **Capacity Building:** Provide training and capacity-building initiatives to local personnel, including coast guards, maritime authorities, and community members, to enhance their skills in operating and maintaining surveillance systems and contribute to regional empowerment.

Continuous Improvement and Innovation:

- **Research and Development:** Invest in research and development efforts to advance the capabilities and effectiveness of SMAUG, including the integration of emerging technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence, machine learning) and the enhancement of data analytics and decision support tools.

By incorporating these sustainability considerations into the planning and implementation, stakeholders can promote environmentally responsible practices and ensure the long-term viability and effectiveness of the solution. All outcomes of the Exploitation Plan will be documented in **D7.3 Exploitation & Sustainability Report** at Month 18 and **D7.5 Exploitation & Sustainability Report** at Month 36.

5. Conclusions

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies in Horizon Europe projects are structured to extend the impact of projects beyond research outcomes alone. In pursuit of this objective, **SMAUG** has devised a comprehensive master plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation. This plan delivers the crucial elements of these strategies that must be upheld throughout the project's lifespan. The current document is anticipated to serve as a cornerstone for ongoing and anticipated **communication, dissemination, and exploitation** activities, with all activities continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's duration.

In terms of communication and dissemination, **SMAUG** aims to share project results across various phases with the appropriate audiences at the right junctures to showcase how research and innovation contribute to a **European 'Innovation Union'**. Communication initiatives will highlight the scientific excellence and competitive contributions of our multidisciplinary European consortium. The plan is tailored to the diverse nature of consortium members, enabling targeted outreach to different segments of stakeholders. Selected channels will **ensure broad visibility** and project enhancement through impactful marketing tools, including **social networks, events, external media, publications, conferences, and email marketing**.

Simultaneously, public relations campaigns are designed **to keep stakeholders informed of SMAUG's progress and outcomes**. All activities will adhere to the established image and convey the appropriate messages, ensuring that all communications resonate with the project's overarching goals. To verify the effectiveness of these efforts, **a metrics system** has been devised to gauge results and align them with predefined objectives.

Concerning exploitation, **SMAUG's consortium** will persistently assess and evaluate project outcomes, explore potential exploitation avenues, and pinpoint the most promising pathways for each asset. Various routes, such as individual or collaborative exploitation, **scientific, commercial and technical exploitation**, will be scrutinized to determine the optimal course of action for **sustainable impact** beyond the project's timeframe. Additionally, proactive management of intellectual property rights for the project's research findings will ensure their proper **valuation and preservation**, potentially generating revenue for involved partners post-project completion.

6. ANNEX

Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Type of KPI		Target KPI	
Communication	Website Traffic	300 unique visitors/month	Measure every four months
	Social media	1500+ followers	Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube followers
	Non-Scientific Articles	30+	Publications in articles, blog posts, position papers, factsheets and other non-scientific publications
	Open Access Downloads	1000+	Downloads of public deliverables and documentation through ZENODO
	Webinars & Workshops	8+ 500+ participants	These events facilitate hands-on training and exchange of ideas related to the modules, providing opportunities for round table discussions, mentoring and development.
	Newsletters	13	Nine internal and four external
	Videos	3	Showcasing on results, partners or interviews
Dissemination	Peer-Reviewed Publications	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •10 Journals •10 Conferences
		400+ citations	
	Conferences & Events	14+	Showcases results achieved by the project through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces and personal engagement.
Ecosystem Building	Networks of Contact points	1000+	Overall contacts with whom the project will contact to
	Synergies	4+	Create synergies on joint events, workshops, joint publications, etc.

Table 14. Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Communication Tools

SMAUG Website (<https://smaug-horizon.eu/>) has been operational since December 2023 and consists of six distinct pages focused on the project presentation, consortium, use cases, activities, and publications.

Our Mission

The **SMAUG** project is on a mission to improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes, leveraging the power of **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, using an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat **detection and analysis** between 3 main elements:

Figure 11. SMAUG Website Home Page

The first set of articles and deliverables are featured on the website's "[Activities](#)" and "[Publications](#)" pages.

Figure 12. SMAUG Website Activities Page

D7.1

The SMAUG LinkedIn page has been operational since **October 2023** and has already garnered **275 followers** in less than three months. Three new posts are shared on this channel every week.

Figure 13. SMAUG LinkedIn Page

D7.1

The project has been active on the second social media channel, X, since **October 2023**. Currently, the project has **259 followers** on X. We regularly post new content on this channel three times a week.

Figure 14. SMAUG X/Twitter Page

The **four-pager and roll-up** resumes for the **SMAUG** project outline its main objectives and actions. These documents are valuable for engaging with stakeholders during **meetings, events, and other one-on-one interactions**.

Project details

Duration: 36 months
 Starting date: 1 October 2023
 Call: HORIZON-CL3-2022-BM-01
 Project coordinator: INDRA SISTEMAS SA (INDRA)

SMAUG team

22 organisations, including universities, SMEs, research organisations, public institutions as well as customs, are on board to achieve the maximum results and impact of the SMAUG objectives, offering their unique expertise and knowledge

SMAUG

Smart Maritime And Underwater Guardian

The SMAUG project's mission is to improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes by utilising artificial intelligence (AI) and an integrated system that can provide data regarding threat detection and analysis between three main elements:

- Ports security infrastructure
- Advanced underwater detection systems
- Surveillance vessels

SMAUG's social world

Discover the SMAUG project!

QR code, X, in, YouTube icons and handles: @SMAUG_EU, @SMAUG_EU, @SMAUG_EU, info@smaug-horizon.eu

SMAUG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101121129

Funded by the European Union

Figure 15. SMAUG Four-Pager

SMAUG will improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes, leveraging the power of **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**, using an **integrated system** capable of providing data concerning threat detection and analysis between **3 main elements**

Underwater detection & location
will be performed by 4 primary methods:

- Acoustic detection
- High-resolution sonar inspection
- Rapid sonar hull scan
- Collective autonomous location

SMAUG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101121129

Figure 16. SMAUG Roll-up (Banner)

Outreach & Branding Guidelines

Communication and dissemination activities are crucial for the success of the SMAUG project. Given their importance, all consortium partners must contribute and engage in these activities, promoting the project's objectives, actions, and achievements. These guidelines are created to assist you in implementing any dissemination and communication activity.

*To share your communication and outreach updates, ask any questions or provide suggestions about them or these guidelines, please get in touch with us at smaug@australo.org

1. Internal communication

The main internal communication channels of the SMAUG project, where all information related to dissemination and communication activities will be shared, are:

- Email: smaug@australo.org
- Microsoft Teams: **Execution**. This channel allows us to have a shared repository with the project's documents and to maintain agile communication. The outreach and branding materials will be saved in the teams: **Execution / Files / 03.WPs & Tasks / WP7 – Outreach & Exploitation folder**. *The material that can be shared publicly will also be uploaded to the open-access repository [Zenodo](#)

Figure 17. SMAUG Outreach & Branding Guidelines

An internal Media Release Form was issued to all project partners for permission to use photos and/or videos of **SMAUG consortium partners** throughout the duration of the project.

SMAUG

SMAUG EU Project- Informed Consent for Multimedia Use

Welcome!

As part of the SMAUG EU project activities, photos, videos and audio recordings may be captured during conferences and other project related events for promotional and dissemination-related purposes in print materials and on the Internet (social media and official website)

By filling in this form, you agree to having your image and/or video and/or voice recorded and published for project's related activities. You can retract your consent at any time by sending an email with Title: Unsubscribe at info@smaug-horizon.eu

Your name *

Your last name *

Organisation *

Position *

E-mail *

Social Media Profile *

Do you agree to the terms outlined above? *

 YES NO

Figure 18. Informed Consent Form

SMAUG utilises the **Zenodo OpenAIRE+⁴** repository for depositing publications and data, with tools available to establish connections between them. The Zenodo infrastructure serves as a document repository for all public deliverables. Whenever feasible, datasets are openly shared through data.europa.eu, the EU's official data portal.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the SMAUG_Horizon Europe Project. The top navigation bar includes a search bar, 'Communities', 'My dashboard', and a user profile for 'smaug@a...'. The project page features a 'New upload' button and navigation tabs for 'Records', 'Requests', 'Members', and 'Settings'. A sidebar on the left provides filters for 'Versions', 'Access status', 'Resource types', 'Subjects', 'File type', and 'Help'. The main content area shows 6 results found, sorted by 'Newest'. The records listed are:

- January 31, 2024 (v1)** Other Open: Roll-up - SMAUG EU Project (Martinelli, Dario), uploaded March 7, 2024. 7 views, 1 download.
- January 31, 2024 (v1)** Other Open: Brochure - SMAUG EU Project (Martinelli, Dario), uploaded March 4, 2024. 7 views, 10 downloads.
- February 21, 2024 (v1)** Other Open: 1st Newsletter - SMAUG EU Project (Marva, Arampatzis, Sapountzis, Antonis), SMAUG Project Consortium, uploaded March 4, 2024. 10 views, 16 downloads.
- October 18, 2023 (v1)** Other Open: SMAUG Branding Elements (Martinelli, Dario), uploaded February 29, 2024. 5 views, 10 downloads.
- December 22, 2023 (v01)** Project deliverable Open: SMAUG - D1.2 Consultation Strategy (Indira (Spain)), uploaded December 22, 2023. 20 views, 31 downloads.
- November 3, 2023 (v1.0)** Project milestone Open: SMAUG Project - 1st Press Release (SMAUG Consortium; Sapountzis, Antonis; Arampatzis, Marva), uploaded November 3, 2023. 27 views, 48 downloads.

Figure 19. SMAUG Zenodo Repository

⁴ zenodo.org/communities/smaugeuproject

EU logo and acknowledgement

As recipients of EU funding, we have to use the [European flag](#) and emblem in our communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programs.

Adaptions of this acknowledgement text depending on what is needed for deliveries or submissions.

	SMAUG has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101121129.
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EU disclaimer

It is also necessary the inclusion of the disclaimer in any document delivered within the scope of the project — a statement that denies liability and is intended to prevent civil liability arising from certain acts or omissions.

The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Text can appear on the right, left, bottom or top, depending on the needs, and in various fonts.

For more information, please follow the [guidelines](#) on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU funding and apply the indicated [graphic rules](#).